

EFFECT OF NICOTINAMIDE ON MOOD IN DEPRESSED MICE USING OPEN FIELD TEST MODEL OF DEPRESSION

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Abstract

*Depression is a mental health disorder that disrupt person's behaviors, thoughts and his physical health. It is characterized by sadness, loss of interest or pleasure, feelings of guilt or low self-worth, disturbed sleep or/and appetite, feelings of tiredness, and poor concentration (World Health Organization, 2017). The world health organization has ranked depression as the 4th leading cause of disability in the world and is projected to be the 2nd by the year 2020. In Nigeria, about 3.9% of the populations suffer from depression. Nicotinamide (NAM), may increase the level of nicotinamide adenine dinucleotide (NAD) which lead to the activation of Sirtuins enzyme leading to anti-depressant activity (Sampath et al., 2015). The aim of this study was to investigate the antidepressant effect of nicotinamide on mood in depressed mice using open field test model of depression. Twenty-five mice of both sexes were randomly divided into five groups of five animals each, group I received normal saline 10mg / k * g group II, III and IV received 25mg / k * g 50mg / k * g 100mg / k * g of NAM respectively and group V received 20mg / k * g * fluoxetine. Tail suspension test (TST) was carried out on the animals before treatment which served as a baseline for depression. The animals were habituated to swimming for 4 days and on the fifth day, drug administration commenced which lasted for two weeks. The animals were only allowed to swim on the 1st x 4th Box 7th, 10th and 14th day. Behavioral despair (immobility time), locomotor activity and anxiety of animals were assessed using tail suspension test, open space force swim test (OSFST) and open field test (OFT). The result obtained showed a statistically significant difference ($p < 0.05$) in 4th day of OSFST between group two and five and also on the 7th day of OSFST between group five when compared with group one and group two. There was no statistically significant difference in mobility of TST ($p > 0.05$) and also in the parameters taken (line crossing, center crossing, rearing, grooming, fecal bolus, and urine drops) using OFT ($p > 0.05$) between the control and NAM treated groups. In conclusion, the result showed that NAM has no statistically significance on mood in depressed mice using OFT.*

Introduction

Depression is a mental health disorder that disrupt person's behaviors, thoughts and his physical health. It is characterized by sadness, loss of interest or pleasure, feelings of guilt or low self-worth, disturbed sleep or/and appetite, feelings of tiredness, and poor concentration (World Health Organization, 2017). Depression is said to be present if these symptoms or other persists for two weeks. It may be recurrent or chronic, and lead to strong impairment in an individual ability to take care of his everyday responsibilities. Depression is different from feelings of intense grief brought about by the death of loved ones, because these

are normal reactions to life stresses that with time and usually without medical treatment disappears. Unlike the depression that without medical treatment often tend to persist (Bhowmik et al., 2012).

Anxiety is a general term for several disorders that is characterized by nervousness, fear, apprehension, and worrying which affects regularly occurring emotions (such as happiness, excitement, hope, anger, surprise, etc.) that can be observed throughout all human cultures and in several animal species. Some of the actual most prominent medical and public health problems is the comorbidity of anxiety and depression (Damasio and Carvalho, 2013).

Nicotinamide (the amide form of Vitamin B1) is believed to cause an improvement in the energy production due to its role as a precursor of nicotinamide adenosine dinucleotide (NAD), an important molecule involved in energy metabolism. Various research has shown the potent role of nicotinamide towards the increasing level of neurotransmitter GABA (Miura and Kameda, 2005). Side effects of nicotinamide are minimal, though at high doses liver problems may occur (MacKay et al., 2012) Normal amounts are safe for use during pregnancy (Retrieved from <https://www.drugs.com/pregnancy/nicotinamide.html>, 2016). Foods that contain nicotinamide include yeast, meat, milk, and green vegetables.

Nicotinamide may increase the level of nicotinamide adenine dinucleotide (NAD) which lead to the activation of sirtuins (an enzyme which deacetylates proteins that contribute to cellular regulation) causing the anti-inflammatory effect which ultimately result into anti-depressant activity (Sampath et al., 2015).

Statement of Research Problem

Globally, the total number of people with depression was estimated to exceed 300 million in 2015 and nearly that number again suffers from a range of anxiety disorders in comorbid form with depression (WHO, 2017). The consequences of these disorders in terms of lost health are huge. Depression is ranked by WHO in 2017 as the largest contributor to global disability, while anxiety disorders are ranked 6th (3.4%). Depression in comorbid with anxiety is also the major contributor to suicide deaths, which the number is close to 800 000 per year (WHO, 2017).

The proportion of the global population with anxiety disorders in 2015 is estimated to be

3.6%. As with depression, anxiety disorders are more common among females than males (4.6% compared to 2.6% at the global level). The total estimated number of people living with anxiety disorders together with depression across the world is 264 million. This total for 2015 reflects a 14.9% increase since 2005, as a result of population growth and ageing (Global burden analysis, 2015).

It is estimated that by 2030 depression related morbidity rates will rise, and depression as one of the leading causes of disability will increase in significance in the total burden of disease (Milanovic et al., 2015).

Justification of the Study

Anxiety in comorbid with depression is among the disorders that are believed to be the major challenges concerning health issues all over the world. It is also considered among 6th most prevalent disorders that affect about 40 million American adults aged 18years and older per year causing them to be filled with fearfulness and uncertainty (Kessler et al, 2005). In Nigeria, the prevalence of anxiety among the general population appears to be 4.4% (Yussuf, 2005)

This study evaluates how nicotinamide may be better by increasing the level of nicotinamide adenine dinucleotide (NAD) so that SIRT1 (an enzyme which deacetylates proteins that contribute to cellular regulation) will be activated causing the inhibition of the inflammatory factors release, resulting into anti-depressant activity (Sampath et al., 2015). Foods that contain nicotinamide include yeast, meat, milk, and green vegetables.

Aim and Objectives

Aim: The aim of this study was to determine the effect of nicotinamide on anxiety disorder

using Open Field Test (OFT) model in depressed mice.

Specific Objectives

- i. To evaluate the effect of nicotinamide on anxiety disorder in depressed mice using Open Field Test (OFT) model.
- ii. To induce depression on mice using open space forced swim test (OSFST).

To evaluate the anti-depressant like potential of nicotinamide on hopefulness activity of depressed mice using Tail Suspension Test (TST).

Hypothesis

Ho Nicotinamide has no effect on mood in depressed mice.

Materials and Methods

Drug preparation

Nicotinamide (BDH, laboratories) of 100mg/kg with stock concentration of 10mg/ml that was converted to 0.06g was dissolved in 6ml of distilled water, after which was followed by serial dilutions. 3ml was taken from the prepared solution and put in separate preparation bottle, 3ml of distilled water was then added and mixed to make 50mg/kg of nicotinamide. Another 25mg/kg of nicotinamide was prepared by taking 3ml of the solution of 50mg/kg of nicotinamide and mixing it with 3ml of distilled water in another separate bottle. Therefore, the various doses of 25mg/kg, 50mg/kg and 100mg/kg of the nicotinamide prepared were administered orally to group two, group three and group four respectively, for consecutive two weeks.

Fluoxetine (V.S international Pvt. Ltd, india) of 10mg was dissolved in 5ml of distilled water. A dose of 20mg/kg that was obtained from the stock concentration of 2mg/ml was

administered to group five orally for 14 consecutive days (two weeks).

A normal saline dose of 10ml/kg was administered to group one for two consecutive weeks.

Animals Used

Twenty-five Mice weighing from 14-28g were used for this research. The animals were obtained from the Faculty of Veterinary Medicine, Department of Physiology, Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria. The animals were housed in the animal house of the Department of Human Physiology, Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria Nigeria. They were kept in cages under normal environmental temperature and were allowed to acclimatize for two weeks before the onset of the experiment. The mice were fed with vital feeds growers mesh and water ad libitum.

Experimental Design

The mice were randomly divided in to five groups comprising of five animals each

Group 1: served as the control group which received 10ml/kg of normal saline for two weeks and were exposed to open space forced swim test.

Group 2: received 25mg/kg of Nicotinamide for two weeks and were exposed to open space forced swim test.

Group 3: received 50mg/kg of Nicotinamide for two weeks and were exposed to open space forced swim test.

Group 4: received 100mg/kg of Nicotinamide for two weeks and were exposed to open space forced swim test.

Group 5: received 20mg/kg of Fluoxetine for two weeks and were exposed to open space forced swim test.

Neurobehavioral Studies

Open-field test (OFT)

The study was conducted according to method previously described by Brown et al. (1999) with some modifications. The apparatus was made up of plywood, measuring 72 cm x 72 cm x 36 cm. One of the walls was made of Plexiglas to ensure visibility of the mouse under observation. The floor, made of cardboard was divided into 16 equal squares (18 cm x 18 cm) with black marker and a central square drawn with red marker. The cardboard was covered with a transparent Plexiglas to ensure that faeces and urine were easily removed. The experimental mice were placed at one of the four corners of the open field and allowed to explore the apparatus for 5 minutes and their behaviour is recorded. The behavioural parameters taken include line crossing, centre crossing, rearing, grooming, faeces and urine drops. The apparatus was wiped between observations with spirit and allowed to dry to remove any olfactory cue (Magaji et al., 2011).

Open space force swim test

The method of this test was adapted from that of Stone and Lin, 2011. The method consists of exposing mice to swimming daily in warm water (32-34°C) in tub cages 24 * 43 * 23 cm wh * 1 for 15 min/day for 4 days, and thereafter swum on 1 n, 4 deg 7th, 10th, and 14 ^ (th) * day with the treatment for 2 weeks. The tub cage was divided in to four quadrants and one quadrant is maintained when placing the mice of respective group and record was taken on distance swum and immobility (floating) time of the mice.

Tail suspension test (TST)

TST is a test conducted to test the antidepressant potentials of drugs, or to test the

result of experimental manipulations proposed to affect depression related behaviours. The apparatus was made up of ply wood of suspension box with total dimension (55height * 60wi * dth * 11.5cm * depth) The suspension box is divided in to six compartments with dimension (55height x 15width x 11.5cm depth). Tape of 17cm long was used and the tail of the mice was place on 2cm mark with 2-3millimeter of tail remaining outside the tape. With the climb stopper on the tail, the Mice were suspended by placing the free end of the tape on the suspension bar. The duration of immobility was recorded during a period of 6 minutes. White noise generator was used to mask the intermittent environmental sound. The suspension compartment was wiped between observations with spirit and allowed to dry to remove any olfactory cue (Silva et al., 2013).

Result

Effect of Nicotinamide on Immobility Using Open Space Force Swim Test

Table 4.1 Effect of nicotinamide on immobility time using OSFST

Treatment groups (mg/kg)	IMM time day 1	IMM time day 4	IMM time day 7	IMM time day 10	IMM time day 14
Normal saline	523.0±40.6	356.6±50.88	151.0±72.90 ^a	190.2±84.83	286.2±78.16
NAM (25)	467.6±53.97	221.60±131.96 ^b	181.6±77.15 ^c	198.4±83.07	310.2±93.10
NAM (50)	639.20±62.91	545.00±82.67	487.0±102.55	466.2±79.45	563.0±22.21
NAM (100)	546.40±82.54	492.80±90.99	519.8±70.93	448.8±115.35	575.4±138.73
Fluoxetine (20)	583.20±50.66	590.80±50.23 ^b	563.8±116.57 ^c	535.8±124.98	591.2±97.25

^a the mean difference is significant when compared with group five on day 4, $p < 0.05$, $n=5$.

^b the mean difference is significant when compared with group two on day 4, $p < 0.05$, $n=5$.

^c the mean difference is significant when compared with group one and two on day 7, $p < 0.05$, $n=5$.

^e the mean difference is significant when compared with group five on day 7, $p < 0.05$, $n=5$.

^d the mean difference is significant when compared with group five on day 7, $p < 0.05$, $n=5$.

Figure 4.2 Effect of Nicotinamide on behavioural despair (immobility time) in Tail Suspension Test (TST) before treatment.

The mean difference is not statistically significant when compared with Normal saline group. Result presented as mean ±SEM; $p > 0.05$, $n=5$. NAM- Nicotinamide.

Discussion, conclusion and recommendation

Discussion

Open space forced swim test (OSFST) was used to induce depression and there was no difference observed. The study revealed that there is no difference in immobility time between the treatment groups and control using open space force swim test for the duration of 14 days. However, we have observed some

statistical significance on day four and seven, but it was between the treatment groups and not with normal saline group. This shows that subjecting the animals to swim for 15 minutes might not be enough to induce depression in mice. Moreover, subjecting them to OSFST for 14 days might also not be enough to induce depression in them. However, Stone and Lin (2011) proved that two-weeks exposure to OSFST is enough to induce depression in animals. Nonetheless, our finding doesn't corroborate with their finding.

Similarly, similar trend was observed in tail suspension test (TST) in which there was no significance observed between the control group and the treatment group both at baseline and after subjecting the animals to stressors i.e. OSFST. To further confirm the effect of the nicotinamide on immobility time, the animals were subjected to Open Field Test to assess the effect of the intervention (nicotinamide) on anxiety in depressed mice, but the study showed that the intervention does not have effect on anxiety.

The lack of effect of model and/or nicotinamide on the behaviour of the animals might not necessarily indicate that the animals were not depressed as behaviour is more robust to changes. Biochemical analysis measuring markers of depression might depict definitive presence and/or absence of depression. However, we are constrained with resources to conduct the biochemical analysis.

Conclusion

At the end of this study, it was observed that open space forced swim test (OSFST) doesn't induce behavioural changes associated with depression in the mice. However, nicotinamide might hold potential benefit as antidepressant. The lack of effect of OSFST on behavioural changes associated with depression makes the

effect of nicotinamide on the depression model unclear.

Recommendation

1. Other models of inducing depression should be explored to assess the nicotinamide antidepressant potential.

11. Further studies on open space forced swim test should consider increasing the time and days of swimming of the animals.

III. Biochemical analysis should be carried out to assess the level of biomarkers for depression.

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